

FINITE ELEMENT AIDED DESIGN OF LAMINATED AND SANDWICH PLATES

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ABSTRACT

The classical finite element programs are not well suited to the design of composite structures, because they are primarily analysis tools and need much time for the input and the processing of the data and the interpretation of the results. The aim of the present work was to develop a program giving very fast analyses in order to make possible the design process of a structure through the re-analysis of this structure under slightly modified conditions (loads, boundary conditions, materials properties). Speed in the analysis has been obtained by : simplification of the analysed structure and limitations in its generality, improvements in the numerical methods used, selection of easy-to-use and efficient computers or micro-computers, development of a user-friendly software. The program FEAD-LASP (Finite Element Aided Design for Laminated And Sandwich Plates) was developed from parts of a rather classical finite element program for microcomputer. It is limited to rectangular geometries (composite and sandwich panels in bending and in-plane deformation) and pre-defined regular meshes, but takes into account completely general boundary and load conditions. Generality is also available for the material properties, which include bending, in-plane, bending-membrane coupling and transverse shear stiffnesses (extended laminated plate theory, i.e. classical laminated plate theory plus shear effects). A 16-node thick plate element with transverse shear, in which the materials properties of the laminate or sandwich are input using an equivalent material, was retained. A faster method for the formation and assembly of the stiffness matrices of the elements was derived and tested. It reduces the corresponding time very significantly, using pre-computation and storage of dimensionless parts of the stiffness matrix elements. Several microcomputers and work-stations were used to test the numerical part : it was found that the most powerful personal computers (such as Apple Macintosh II and IBM PC-AT) as well as the low cost work-stations (such as Apollo DN-3000) are well suited for a fast numerical treatment, i.e. only a few minutes for the first analysis, and re-analyses in seconds. A user-friendly input part for the program was developed and makes possible the use of the program by designers with little or no knowledge of the internal structure and methods of the program.

INTRODUCTION

The finite element analyses of structures are currently an important ingredient of the design process for isotropic homogeneous structures. However, for composite structures, a review of existing programs

(general purpose or special purpose programs) shows that generally they are only analysis tools with no design facilities (for more details, the reader is referred to references 1-4). Their use in the design of composite structures highly increases the design cost, due to three important penalties : i) heavy input data (specially for the materials properties) ; ii) long computational time (specially through the re-analysis process, in which the time is in many cases as longer as in the initial analysis) ; and iii) output processing times (related to multilayer structure).

The program FEAD-LASP (Finite Element Aided Design of Laminated And Sandwich Plates) presented in this paper has been built to counter the above drawbacks. Completely developed for the design of laminated and sandwich plates, it was planned and adapted for them. Our principal goals were :

- A. Significant decrease of the computational time, in order to reduce the waiting time for the user,
- B. Fully interactive package, in the sense to be self explanatory and user friendly,
- C. Great generality for the material properties, boundary and loading conditions,
- D. Portability, in the sense of choice of most current and low cost microcomputers and work-stations.

GENERAL DESCRIPTION OF FEAD-LASP

FEAD-LASP is structured around three main levels (Fig. 1) :

1. Fully interactive data input level,
2. Fast finite element analysis level,
3. Interactive re-analysis module.

Fig. 1 : General description of FEAD-LASP program.

The first level (data input) has three independent modules : material properties data, geometrical data and boundary conditions. The second

level is the fast analysis module based on a displacement finite element method. The third level is the re-analysis module operating by modifications of the input data.

The program is written in Fortran 77. It permits the analysis and design of laminated and sandwich plates in linear elasticity. We selected low cost work-stations (Apollo DN-3000 & DN-4000) and two popular microcomputers : Apple Macintosh II, IBM-PC/AT and compatibles in order to have a maximum portability of the software. To run the program satisfactorily, it is necessary to have a graphic display and an arithmetic coprocessor. The minimal required configuration for storage capacity is about 10 Mbytes hard disc drive and 640 Kbytes of RAM memory. However a 20 Mbytes hard disc drive is recommended.

DATA INPUT - TOTAL INTERACTIVE PACKAGE

The data input module was developed to be very easy to understand and self explanatory through the use of total interactivity. The principle is based on Macintosh-like interface technique. Three main independent modules are used in this package (Fig. 1).

The materials properties can take into account the characteristics of general laminated and sandwich plates, including in-plane, bending, bending-membrane coupling and transverse shear stiffnesses. However the geometry is limited to rectangular composite or sandwich panels, which nevertheless covers a wide domain of practical needs.

Boundary conditions are given by specifying zero or prescribed displacements at nodes. Fig.2 illustrates one of the window mouse pull-down menus used for data input.

Fig. 2 Principal pull-down menu for data input.

FAST FINITE ELEMENT ANALYSIS

This part is a major attraction of FEAD-LASP program using the following improvements versus classical finite element programs :

A. A 16-node thick plate finite element (Fig.3), based on the substitution of the real constitutive material by a fictitious

equivalent material, the properties of which are determined from the properties of laminated and sandwich structures (including shear effects), i.e. structures with the following normalized⁵ elastic behaviour :

$$\begin{Bmatrix} N \\ M \\ Q \end{Bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} h A^* & | & \frac{h^2}{2} B^* & | & 0 \\ \hline \frac{h^2}{2} B^* & | & \frac{h^3}{12} D^* & | & 0 \\ \hline 0 & | & 0 & | & h G^* \end{bmatrix} \begin{Bmatrix} \epsilon^o \\ K \\ \gamma \end{Bmatrix}$$

in which N , M and Q are the in-plane forces, bending moments and shear forces, ϵ^o , K and γ are the membrane strains, curvatures and shearing strains, A^* , B^* , D^* and G^* are the normalized in-plane, coupling, bending and shear stiffnesses. The analysis is based on a kinematic and material similarity between these structures and the three dimensional finite element with two nodes in the thickness and elastic stiffnesses varying parabolically along the thickness. This process applied to the finite element method allows to use the classical finite elements in a slightly modified form and avoids resorting to special finite elements⁶.

B. In the assembly process, the speed was enhanced through the use of compact storage (only non-zero terms) of pre-computed dimensionless parts of the global stiffness matrix elements. During the program development, a dimensional analysis, using the fact that a regular mesh was used, showed that only about 10% of the global matrix coefficients in a nondimensional form can generate the global matrix. Consequently, these quantities were computed and stored as data in the program. These data are common to all types of plates, so the assembly process is reduced to the multiplication of different data blocks by dimensional and materials properties. The total number of degrees of freedom is 390 (130 nodes with three degrees of freedom per node).

Fig. 3 The 16-node thick plate finite element used in FEAD-LASP.

REANALYSIS PROCESS

This process is based on the following principles :

A. First, 25 loading cases are solved simultaneously from the beginning. These cases correspond to concentrated normal unit force at each corner node of the elements.

B. Any practical loading can be described as a linear combination of these 25 basic cases. For each loading, the data input process provides the 25 load coefficients and the solution is obtained by the same linear combination of the 25 basic solutions. This combination is almost instantaneous and the process can be re-applied by the designer as many times as required. Also, some current load cases, such as uniform pressure, gravity load, linear load, are pre-defined.

ASSESSMENT OF PERFORMANCES

To illustrate the speed capabilities of FEAD-LASP, an example of plate bending under a central load was investigated. The analysis computational time (level 2, assembly process and solving) was compared with a classical finite element program. Fig.4 shows that, in the case of FEAD-LASP, the assembly process time is eight times less, as well with microcomputers (IBM-PC/AT) as with work-stations (Apollo DN-4000). The solving time is also decreased by about 30%, so the total analysis time is reduced by about 40%. This improvement is when comparison is made to classical analysis run in RAM memory, which is not usual for microcomputer : compared to classical analysis using hard disc drive (which gives times more than 10 minutes), the improvement is even much greater. This comparison shows that the total times vary between 3 to 5 minutes, which is a reasonable analysis time in a design process.

The second study concerns the comparison of times of different steps by running FEAD-LASP on various hardwares. Fig. 5 illustrates this study. It can be seen that, even in the case of very low-cost microcomputers, the total time is reasonable.

Fig. 4 Comparison of analysis computational time (level 2) between classical finite element program and FEAD-LASP using different hardwares (IBM/PC-AT and Apollo DN-4000).

Fig. 5 Comparison of total computational time (level 2 & 3) for FEAD-LASP program running on different hardwares.

CONCLUSIONS

This paper gave a general description and an assessment of FEAD-LASP program. The link of pre- and post-processors (data input and output processing) with the analysis stage (finite elements) to form a design process was described and the attractive features for the user, obtained through significant reductions in processing time and user-friendly package, were emphasized.

Improvements are continuously introduced in this program. Developments in progress plan to introduce artificial intelligence tools, data base managements, efficient material properties description⁷ and optimization techniques in the present version.

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